

KEY INDICATORS

With 223,400 hectares, Ireland had 5% of its farmland under organic management, constituting one of the lowest organic area shares in the European Union. Organic farmland grew almost sevenfold between 2001-2024, thus growing slower than the EU average. Regarding organic retail sales, with 137 million euros, an estimated 2.7% of food retail sales were organic in Ireland, thus below the EU organic share.

ORGANIC FARMLAND

2001

2024

Area* (Share of Total Farmland)

30,017 (0.7%)

223,400 ha (5%)

Area Growth from 2001 to 2024

644.2%

ORGANIC LAND USE & AQUACULTURE

2001

2024

Arable Land* (Share of Total)

2,606 ha (0.2%)

12,283 ha (2.8%)

Permanent Crops* (Share of Total)

N/D

210 ha (11%)

Grassland* (Share of Total)

27,410 ha (0.9%)

210,906 ha (5.2%)

Aquaculture Production (Share of Total)

N/D

34,366 † (97.9%) (2022)

ORGANIC OPERATORS

2001

2024

Producers (Share of Total)

918 (0.7%)

4,999 (3.8%)

Aquaculture Producers

N/D

55

Processors

88

189

Importers

N/D

199

ORGANIC RETAIL SALES

2001

2024

Retail Sales (Share of Total)

25 M €

137 M€ (2.7%)

Per Capita Consumption

6.5 €

31.7 €

Retail Sales Growth from 2001 to 2024

529 %

Imports

N/D

55,125 †

Source: FiBL survey based on national data sources, Eurostat and TRACES/European Commission in the framework of the OrganicTargets4EU project

KEY INDICATORS

DEVELOPMENT OF ORGANIC FARMLAND IN IRELAND

Source: FiBL-AMI Survey, based on Eurostat, Department of Agriculture, Food and the Marine, Nic Lampkin

DEVELOPMENT OF ORGANIC SALES IN IRELAND

Source: FiBL-AMI Survey based on Bord Bia and other national data sources

CAP ORGANIC POLICY SUPPORT

The Ireland CAP strategic plan projects a 4-5 fold increase in organic area and more than 10 times the annual expenditure by 2027 compared with 2018. This substantial increase in expenditure is due in part to a trebling of payment rates per hectare for horticulture and permanent crops, and 25-75% increase in support for arable and grassland. These large increases in support have contributed to a sharp rise in the number of producers converting in 2022 and 2023. Organic farming is prioritised for some other CAP SP measures.

CONVERSION & MAINTENANCE

2018

2027

Land Area Supported (Change from 2018)*	72 kha	337 kha (+368%)
Share of Total Agricultural Area Supported*	1.6%	7.5% (+368%)
Share of Certified Organic Area Supported (Change)*	97%	N/D
Expenditure per Year*	8 M€	89 M€ (+1016%)
Expenditure per Hectare Supported*	111 €	265 € (+139%)

SHARE OF CAP RESOURCES

CAP EXP. 2023-2027 ORGANIC SHARE*

Organic Farming Support (P1)*	256 M€	100%
Eco-Schemes (P1)	1,483 M€	7.9%
Agri-Environment, Climate, Welfare (P2)	1,757 M€	2.6%
Total CAP Expenditure	9,832 M€	

*including in-conversion and fully organic land

CAP ORGANIC CONVERSION AND MAINTENANCE PAYMENTS FOR DIFFERENT LAND USES

INDICATOR	YEAR	FUND	GRASSLAND*	ARABLE CROPS	HORTICULTURE	FRUIT CROPS	ALL AREAS >70HA
Conversion Support (€/ha)	2019	P2	220	260	300	300	
	2023	P2	300	320	800	800	60
Change from 2019 to 2023			36%	+23%	+167%	+167%	
Maintenance Support (€/ha)	2019	P2	170	170	200	200	
	2023	P2	250	270	600	600	30
Change from 2019 to 2023			47%	+59%	+200%	+200%	
Conversion Support Higher than Maintenance	2019		+29%	+53%	+50%	+50%	
	2023		+20%	+19%	+33%	+33%	100%

P1 (Pillar 1) European Agricultural Guarantee Fund (EAGF); P2 (Pillar 2) European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD) and national co-financing

*Additional €50/ha available for organic dairy farmers

NATIONAL ORGANIC ACTION PLAN

The current OAP is Ireland's third since 2008. It is different from most other national OAPs in terms of its focus on individual sub-sectors like milk, meat, arable crops and horticulture. The previous plan was more modest in terms of ambition, both in terms of targets and scope of individual actions. The implementation of the current plan is taking account of the need to respond with information and market to support to the increased rates of conversion stimulated by the higher support payments from 2023.

TARGETS

	PERIOD	LAND AREA TARGET	OTHER TARGETS
Previous Action Plan	2013-15	Unspecified increase	N/D
Current Action Plan	2019-25	10% of UAA by 2030 target set in 2023 Climate Action Plan	Individual sector (dairy, beef, arable etc.) targets

KEY ACTIONS

PREVIOUS ACTION PLAN (2013 - 2015)

CURRENT ACTION PLAN (2019 - 2025)

AQUACULTURE

The organic share of total aquaculture production in Ireland is almost 50%, making Ireland the lead country in Europe. Organic aquaculture has been supported as part of the EMFF (2014-2020) and EMFAF (2021-2027) operational programmes and the Multi-annual National Strategic Plan for Aquaculture, including investment aids, increased competitiveness, research, innovation and knowledge transfer, and high production and certification standards. Addressing regulatory issues for organic aquaculture also featured in the previous national organic action plan. As the funding is project specific and there is no ring-fenced organic budget, statistics on organic aquaculture support expenditure are not available.

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